

YOLOv8-Based Detection of Swimming Pools in the City of Zagreb

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Abstract: This study presents an automated approach for detecting private swimming pools within the administrative boundaries of the City of Zagreb using the YOLOv8 Oriented Bounding Boxes (OBB) object detection framework. The model was trained on manually annotated samples of swimming pools extracted from high-resolution digital orthophotos (30 cm spatial resolution). The training dataset consisted of more than 500 manually annotated swimming pools located in different regions of Croatia, including Istria, continental part, and the Zagreb metropolitan area. The trained model achieved a mean Average Precision of 0.956 (mAP@0.5) and 0.772 (mAP@0.5–0.95) on the validation dataset. The model was subsequently applied to orthophoto tiles covering the City of Zagreb to automatically detect swimming pools across the study area. The detected pools were analysed to investigate their spatial distribution within the city. The results reveal clear spatial patterns, with a significantly higher concentration of pools in low-density residential areas located in the northern districts of Zagreb, particularly in the foothills of Mount Medvednica. The proposed workflow demonstrates the potential of deep learning-based object detection for large-scale urban environment analysis using high-resolution aerial imagery.

Keywords: YOLO OBB; swimming pool detection; digital orthophoto; Zagreb; urban change detection.

1 Introduction

Rapid advances in remote sensing technologies and the increasing availability of high-resolution aerial and satellite imagery have significantly expanded the possibilities for automated spatial analysis. Also, in recent years, deep learning (DL) methods have significantly improved the performance of object detection tasks in remotely sensed imagery. Among modern object detection frameworks, the YOLO (You Only Look Once) family of models has become particularly popular due to its ability to perform fast and accurate object detection in large image datasets (Dobrinić et al. 2025). Among various detectable objects, private swimming pools represent a distinctive feature of residential areas that can serve as an indicator of socio-economic conditions, tourism activity, and patterns of urban development.

Taing (2022) investigated various techniques (e.g., Faster R-CNN, Dynamic Head, CornerNet) to detect the swimming pools in the aerial imagery. More than 3000 swimming pools were used in the training phase, and Dynamic Head model achieved the highest F1 score of 0.94, whereas CornerNet and Faster R-CNN achieved F1 of 0.92 and 0.90, respectively. Authors Cerioni and Meyer from Swiss

Territorial Data Lab (2021) used Mask R-CNN architecture in order to update a register of swimming pools over the canton of Geneva. Their analysis confirms that state-of-the-art DL approaches can effectively assist experts in maintaining up-to-date cadastral information by enabling the detection of previously unknown objects, while also highlighting that domain expertise remains essential despite the use of advanced methods.

In this study, a deep learning-based workflow for the automatic detection of swimming pools from high-resolution aerial orthophotos is developed. A YOLO-based oriented bounding box (OBB) detection model is trained on manually annotated samples and subsequently applied to a large set of orthophoto tiles covering the City of Zagreb. The resulting detections are then analysed to examine the spatial distribution of swimming pools across different administrative units, providing insights into the number of pools per city district, pool density per square kilometre, and the relationship between pool distribution and population density.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The City of Zagreb, the capital of Croatia, is located in the northwestern part of the country at the southern foothills of Mount Medvednica and covers an area of approximately 641 km². The city is characterised by a diverse urban structure that includes densely built central districts, residential neighbourhoods, and suburban areas with lower housing density. Private swimming pools are predominantly located in low-density residential zones, particularly in the northern districts situated on the slopes of Mount Medvednica.

2.2 Data

The analysis was conducted using high-resolution digital orthophotos covering the entire territory of Croatia. The orthophotos were acquired in 2023–2024 with a spatial resolution of 30 cm and were provided by the State Geodetic Administration (2024). For the purposes of DL model training and inference, the imagery was divided into tiles of 2048 × 2048 pixels in the national coordinate reference system (EPSG:3765).

2.3 YOLO OBB model

Swimming pool detection was performed using a DL object detection approach based on the YOLO framework. YOLO models perform object detection in a single forward pass

of the neural network, enabling fast and efficient processing of large image datasets. In this study, the YOLOv8 OBB model was used. Unlike traditional object detection methods that rely on axis-aligned bounding boxes, OBB models allow bounding boxes to be rotated, which better represents the orientation of objects.

The training dataset included more than 500 manually annotated pools from different geographic regions and settlement types to improve the generalization ability of the model. The dataset was divided into training (80%) and validation (20%) subsets. After training, the model was applied to the full set of orthophoto tiles covering the city of Zagreb in order to automatically detect swimming pools across the study area.

2.4 Accuracy assessment

To evaluate the performance of the detection model, several commonly used object detection accuracy metrics were employed. These include Precision (Eq. 1), Recall (Eq. 2), and mean Average Precision (mAP; Eq. 3).

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{mAP} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i \quad (3)$$

where TP, FP, and FN represent the number of true positives, false positives, and false negatives, respectively, and AP denotes average precision.

Precision represents the proportion of correctly detected objects among all detected objects, while recall measures the proportion of correctly detected objects among all ground-truth objects. In addition, the mean Average Precision at different Intersection-over-Union (IoU) thresholds was used to assess detection accuracy. In particular, mAP@0.50 and mAP@0.50–0.95 metrics were analyzed, which are widely used in object detection benchmarks.

These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the detection model by considering both detection accuracy and localization performance. The evaluation was performed using a validation subset of the annotated dataset.

3 Results

The performance of the trained YOLOv8 OBB model was evaluated using a validation subset of the annotated dataset. The model achieved high detection accuracy with a precision of 0.918 and recall of 0.896. The mean Average Precision reached 0.956 at IoU threshold 0.5 and 0.772 across IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0.95 (Table 1).

Table 1. Train results of the YOLOv8 OBB model.

Precision	Recall	mAP@0.5	mAP@0.5-0.95
0.918	0.896	0.956	0.772

The trained model was applied to orthophoto tiles covering the administrative area of the city of Zagreb. In total, 1631 swimming pools were detected within the study area. The spatial distribution of detected pools is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of detected swimming pools in the City of Zagreb.

Table 2. Swimming pools by city district.

District	Count	Pools_km ²	Pools_1000
Brezovica	115	0.9	9.5
Čnomerec	73	3.0	1.9
Donja Dubrava	71	6.6	2.1
Donji grad	0	0.0	0.0
Gornja Dubrava	162	4.0	2.8
Gornji grad - Medveščak	89	8.7	3.4
Maksimir	123	8.2	2.6
Novi Zagreb -east	14	0.8	0.3
Novi Zagreb -west	226	3.6	3.5
Peščenica -Žitnjak	72	2.0	1.4
Podsljeme	117	2.0	6.2
Podsused -Vrapče	158	4.4	3.5
Sesvete	340	2.1	4.8
Stenjevec	30	2.5	0.6
Trešnjevka -south	11	1.1	0.2
Trešnjevka -north	10	1.7	0.2
Trnje	20	2.7	0.5

The number of detected swimming pools varies considerably across the city districts of Zagreb (Table 2). The highest number of pools was detected in Sesvete (340) and Novi Zagreb-West (226). In contrast, central districts such as Donji grad show no detected pools, reflecting the high building density and lack of private residential parcels. Furthermore, the highest pool densities (Pools_km² in Table 2) were in Gornji grad -Medveščak and Maksimir with 8.7 pools/km² and 8.2 pools/km², respectively. These districts are characterised by lower housing density and larger residential parcels, which are more suitable for private pool construction. Also, when considering the number of swimming pools per 1000 inhabitants (Pools_1000 in Table 2), the highest values were recorded in Brezovica with 9.5 pools, and Podsljeme

with 6.2 pools, based on population data obtained from the Croatian Bureau of Statistics (2022), indicating a higher frequency of private pools in less densely populated areas. Overall, the results indicate a clear spatial pattern, with swimming pools predominantly located in suburban districts characterised by lower population density and larger residential parcels.

4 Discussion

This research demonstrated the potential of deep learning-based object detection (i.e., identification of private swimming pools) for large-scale urban environment analysis using high-resolution aerial imagery. Unlike previous models based on axis-aligned bounding boxes (Adegun et al. 2023), the use of OBB improved the detection of small and arbitrarily oriented objects such as swimming pools. As such, within this study, a precision and recall of 0.918 and 0.896 were achieved. Similar results were achieved in the research from Taing (2022), particularly given the increased complexity of the study area and the challenges associated with detecting small and variably oriented objects in dense urban environments.

The spatial analysis of detected swimming pools revealed clear patterns related to urban structure. Although Sesvete has the highest number of swimming pools (340; Table 2), a significantly higher frequency of pools was observed in suburban and low-density residential areas, particularly in

the northern parts of Zagreb, such as Podsljeme and Maksimir. In contrast, central districts such as Donji grad have almost no detected pools due to high building density and the lack of private outdoor space. Furthermore, the analysis of pool density per 1000 inhabitants (Brezovica with 9.5, and Podsljeme with 6.2 pools) further highlight the relationship between swimming pool distribution and urban morphology.

Despite the overall high performance of the model, several limitations were identified. False positive detections were observed in areas with objects visually similar to swimming pools, such as blue rooftops, industrial surfaces, and water bodies. Also, overlapping or occluded objects exacerbate this issue, as YOLO relies on OBB, which can lead to false negatives and overlooked detections (Ali and Zhang 2024). In our research, false negatives occurred in cases where swimming pools were partially covered by vegetation, shadows, or surrounding structures. Small or atypically shaped pools are also more difficult to detect, especially in densely built environments (Wang et al. 2024). False positive and false negative detections were not manually corrected, as the objective was to assess the model performance under fully automated conditions. These errors are therefore considered an inherent limitation of the approach.

Examples of successful and unsuccessful detections are shown in Figure 2. The model performs well in detecting

Figure 2. Examples of correct and incorrect swimming pool detections. (A–B) Correct detections in residential areas; (C) False positive detection over visually similar objects; (D) False negative case where a swimming pool was not detected.

standard rectangular pools in open residential areas, while more complex cases remain challenging.

5 Conclusions

This study presented a deep learning-based approach for the automatic detection of private swimming pools in the City of Zagreb using high-resolution aerial orthophotos. The YOLOv8 OBB model demonstrated high detection accuracy (precision 0.918; recall 0.896) and proved to be suitable for identifying small, oriented objects in complex urban environments.

The results revealed clear spatial patterns in the distribution of swimming pools, with higher concentrations in suburban and low-density residential areas, particularly in the northern parts of the city (Maksimir and Podsljeme). The analysis further showed that swimming pool distribution is strongly related to urban structure, parcel size, and population density.

Future work could focus on improving model generalization through larger and more diverse training datasets, as well as integrating additional data sources to reduce false detections. The approach could also be extended to other types of urban objects or applied to different cities for comparative analysis.

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